

THE IMPORTANCE OF MUSIC IN FORMING THE SPIRITUAL AND MORAL WORLDVIEWS OF STUDENTS.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14835498>

Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the reforms in the field of education, culture, and art in our country, the importance of music in forming the spiritual and moral worldviews and musical perception of young people.

Keywords: spirituality, education, music, art, student, musical sound, national value, musical culture.

Аннотация: В статье дается подробная информация о реформах в сфере образования, культуры и искусства в нашей стране, о значении музыки в формировании духовно-нравственного мировоззрения и музыкального восприятия молодежи.

Ключевые слова: духовность, образование, музыка, искусство, студент, музыкальный звук, национальная ценность, музыкальная культура.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada yurtimizdagi ta'lim, madaniyat, san'at sohasidagi islohotlar, musiqa san'at yoshlarining ma'naviy -axloqiy dunyoqarashlarini va musiqiy idrokni shakllantirishdagi ahamiyati haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ma'naviyat, tarbiya, musiqa, san'at, o'quvchi, musiqiy tovush, milliy qadriyat, musiqa madaniyati.

Music is one of the types of art. Along with painting, architecture, theater and other types of art, music plays an important role in human life. Works of musical art are considered spiritual treasures and give people aesthetic pleasure, serve as spiritual food for them, and educate their aesthetic taste. Music is a constant companion of a person throughout his life. Work done under the sounds of music is productive, and rest with music is enjoyable. People's holidays, weddings, and tragic mourning ceremonies are accompanied by music. Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 " On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom", August 26, 2018 Resolution No. PD - 3920 " On measures for

innovative development of the arts”, Resolution No. PD-4038 of November 28, 2018 “On approval of the Concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan”, 2019 Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1019 of December 19, 2019 “On approval of the Program for improving the activities of museums in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020-2021”, November 23, 2019 Resolution of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 26, 2019 “ On approval of the activities of the Erkin Vakhidov Memorial Museum and the Treasury House-Museum ” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 630 [1] of May 30, 2019 “ On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay”, “Shakhrisabz”, “Termez” and “Kokand” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 Decisions of this nature being taken by our government are another important step towards the future of our country, the youth[2], 2020 “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 “ Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3], 2020 “On measures to further enhance the role and influence of the arts in society ” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 325 of June 9, 2021 and “Martyrs’ Memory” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 357 of February 2, 2022 “On support of the Moat Fund” The normative legal acts adopted, such as Resolution No. PD - 112 of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan [4] are becoming increasingly important.

Music is a type of art that reflects a person's emotional experiences, thoughts, and imagination through a sequence or set of musical sounds (tones, melodies). Its content consists of certain musical artistic images that express changing mental states. Music embodies various human moods (emotion, joy, pleasure, contemplation, sadness, fear, and others).

In addition, music vividly reflects the volitional qualities of a person (determination, aspiration, thoughtfulness, restraint, etc.), his nature (custom).

The musical culture of the Uzbek people has a very long history. In the course of historical development, such forms and styles of performance as folk classical music, traditional professional music, folk compositional methods, as well as folklore - amateur musical heritage, have complemented each other. This musical heritage is still manifested today as a part of our spiritual culture. With the advent of independence, the process of revitalizing our national and spiritual values, customs, and historically valuable traditions that are being forgotten has become a priority.

The process of revitalizing our national values, customs, and spiritual wealth has been raised to the state level. From the first years of independence, much has been done to preserve and restore the spiritual wealth left by our ancestors, including musical culture, and to keep pace with the times. In this regard, the main factor is our immense spiritual wealth, which our ancestors have bequeathed to us.

It is known from history that our musical culture, traditional songs, and maqom performances, which are the main link of our spirituality, have always been recognized as spiritual nourishment in the daily life of our people. The people sought salvation from music in difficult times, and songs and music accompanied them in happy times. Highly qualified employees working here are ready to show dedication in any situation[5]. Therefore, on this blessed day of independence, at a time when we are realizing our identity, it is natural to rely on our national musical culture, which is a part of our great spirituality, inherited from our ancestors, and to turn to our traditional songs. All of this is of great importance in the harmonious upbringing of the generation and in the formation of the spiritual worldview of young people. Our traditional music and songs have always called people to faith, love, and humanity. Even today, without losing this relevance, they remain one of the main factors in the path to independence, the formation of the consciousness of working people, and the harmonious upbringing of the next generation. The art of singing, music, dance, and folklore performance are considered ancient art forms that emerged and developed in close connection with the life and creativity of the people of the national musical art. In particular, the songs of our people in the traditional spirit are an immortal heritage and, as in all times, today respond. But at the same time, it is natural that creating songs that are not only a tribute to history, but also in line with the spirit of today, is an important task for all specialists and artists involved in musical art, which is one of the main factors in the development of our national ideology.

Our country is beginning a completely new society, a new way of life and a new life. Changes have occurred in the hearts, thinking and imagination of our people. As our President emphasized, the issue of spirituality includes many factors, such as the history of the nation, moral and religious values, cultural heritage, traditions and customs, national ideology, patriotism and humanity, awareness of national identity, and ultimately serves as the main criterion in determining the identity of a person. Spirituality and enlightenment have always been the strongest characteristic of our people throughout their centuries-old

history. Based on these principles, it is necessary for all areas of spiritual life to determine their goals and objectives. In this regard, it is especially important to assess the special place of musical culture in spiritual life, to understand that its main criterion is the direction of its influence towards the ideology of independence. Today, cultural life is experiencing shifts in accordance with this principle. We will not be mistaken if we say that the thoughts of creators are directed towards these principles. Musical culture is distinguished by its diversity. The ancient peasants settled around this spring. [6] In particular, the rich musical heritage of the Uzbek people, whose roots go back to ancient times, has not left our daily lives. It includes high examples of folk art, folklore performance, melodic structure, richly developed instrumental and vocal works, epic performance, and a complex performance genre called makom music.

Since ancient times, music has been widely used in all systems of education and upbringing as a powerful educational tool. Pedagogical technology is an important means of engaging and interacting with students to ensure the success of learning [7]. Prominent statesmen, scientists, and teachers have considered all types of art, including music, as a means of forming and developing high spiritual qualities in people, deeply influencing their minds and souls, and have attached great importance to it. Each genre of musical art contains such content that expresses the spirit of a country, people, and humanity in a particular period. The power of musical works lies in their truthfulness and intelligibility, in their ability to emotionally affect the inner spiritual world of people. It is important to take this characteristic of musical art into account when raising a well-rounded generation.

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